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Review Article

**A REVIEW ON APPLICATIONS OF THERMOGRAVIMETRIC
METHODS OF ANALYSIS (TGA, DTA, DSC)****Sivanaga Tejaswini Naredla¹, K. Purna Nagasree*¹, Y. Pooja¹, V. Uma Maheswari¹,
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Vishakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh-531162, India²College of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam – 530003 Andhra
Pradesh, India**Article Received: July 2024****Accepted: July 2024****Published: August 2024****Abstract:**

Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA), Differential Thermal Analysis (DTA), and Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) are pivotal thermal analysis techniques with extensive applications across various scientific and industrial fields. TGA is a versatile analytical technique used to study the thermal stability and composition of materials by monitoring changes in weight as a function of temperature. TGA is crucial for characterizing polymers, composites, and nanomaterials, providing insights into decomposition temperatures, compositional analysis, and the effects of additives or fillers. TGA measures the change in mass of a material as a function of temperature or time under a controlled atmosphere, providing critical insights into thermal stability, composition, and decomposition mechanisms. DTA detects temperature differences between a sample and a reference under identical thermal conditions, enabling the characterization of phase transitions, crystallization, and thermal behavior. DSC, a refinement of DTA, quantitatively measures the heat flow associated with transitions in materials, facilitating precise determination of melting points, glass transitions, specific heat capacities, and reaction kinetics. Together, these techniques are instrumental in material science for the development of polymers, pharmaceuticals, and composites; in quality control for determining purity and compositional analysis; and in the study of environmental effects and degradation processes. Their integration offers a comprehensive understanding of thermal properties, essential for innovation and optimization in material design and application.

Key Words: TGA, DTA, DSC, purity, thermal properties.

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INTRODUCTION:

Thermal analysis has a history spanning over eleven decades, during which various techniques have been developed and applied across numerous fields. Today, thermal analysis is utilized in the study of minerals, inorganic substances, metals, ceramics, electronic materials, polymers, organic substances, pharmaceuticals, foodstuffs, and biological organisms. Initially employed in research, its applications have progressively extended into development and the control of processes and quality in these diverse areas [1]. Thermal analysis techniques are particularly valuable for studying the properties of polyphasic systems, including drug substances and excipients, and play a unique role in developing new delivery systems [2]. These techniques are employed across a wide range of disciplines, from pharmacy and food science to polymer science, materials science, and glass technology—essentially any field where changes in sample behavior are observed under controlled heating or cooling conditions. The broad range of measurements enabled by thermal analysis provides fundamental information on the material properties of the system under examination. Consequently, thermal analysis has seen increasing use in the basic characterization of materials and across a wide spectrum of applications in research, development, and quality control within both industry and academia [3].

Thermal analysis encompasses a range of techniques in which a sample's property is continuously measured while it undergoes a predetermined temperature profile.

The Common Techniques:

1. Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA)
2. Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)
3. Differential Thermal Analysis (DTA)

I. THERMOGRAVIMETRIC ANALYSIS (TGA):

Thermogravimetry (TGA) is a dynamic technique that combines gravimetric analysis with oven drying. It

continuously records both the weight of a specimen and the temperature of a small oven over time until the specimen reaches a constant weight. This continuous recording highlights anomalies in water release and the temperatures at which these anomalies occur, such as the release of crystallization water or condensation reactions. Additionally, it identifies the onset of degradation mechanisms accompanied by gas emissions, such as CO₂ or NH₃. The TGA apparatus can be connected to a computer for advanced data processing and analysis. TGA is more sophisticated than traditional gravimetry, offering interpretive insights into the final readings, faster processing, and requiring smaller specimens. As some of the most important analytical methods, thermal analysis techniques have significantly advanced due to the demands of materials characterization. Over the past four decades, major developments in this field have been driven by the computerization of thermal analysis techniques. In the next 20 years, thermal analysis techniques are expected to continue evolving in at least two distinct directions. First, with a small additional effort, traditional thermal analysis techniques can achieve more precise measurements. This will yield new information about a material's structure, interface, and morphology. Second, thermal analysis techniques can be integrated with other in-situ temperature-controlled experiments, such as diffraction, scattering, microscopy, and spectroscopy, to investigate the structure and dynamics of materials. This will generate information of the structural evolution with changing thermal properties and therefore, greatly aid in the understanding of structure-property relationships of the materials [6]. Thermo gravimetric method is a common method for evaluating degradation. TGA is used to measure changes by mass by heating the sample over a temperature range at a specified rate, heating the sample at specified temperature for a selected time. Mass decrease will occur upon solvent/water loss and when volatile degradation products are formed.

Figure 1: Instrumentation of TGA

APPLICATIONS OF TGA

TGA is relevant to most sectors and environmental research. The primary applications of thermogravimetric analysis and evolved gas analysis are in food science, pharmaceuticals, and petrochemicals. Thermogravimetric analysis is a valuable technique for determining not only the thermal stability of diverse substances, but also the structure of insoluble and infusible compounds. TGA can be used to calculate a substance's mass change owing to breakdown, oxidation, evaporation, or combustion. The absorbed moisture content, material volatilization rate, and thermal breaking point of base fluids or formulations contained inside the substance.

1. Thermal stability determination

TGA can be used to treat a product, such as plastic, gas, or glue, to a temperature range in which it must operate while in use, in order to guarantee that the product performs as expected throughout its normal use.

2. Oxidation and combustion research for product storage and use

TGA is commonly used to research oxidation processes since they are clearly observable and quantifiable, particularly in goods like copper alloys that require strong oxidation resistance. When a sample is heated with TGA, it often loses bulk. Both oxidation and combustion studies are critical for

defining how items should be kept, distributed, manufactured, and used in practice. The TGA is routinely used to examine pharmaceutical items prior to their approval for distribution and patient usage.

3. TGA to delineate the hot melt extrusion chemical stability processing window

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) is widely used to determine the allowable processing temperatures for hot melt extrusion. Active pharmaceutical ingredients (API) and excipients are subjected to high temperatures during hot melt extrusion (HME). The thermal stability of these components is critical for the production of a medicinal product with the right identification, strength, quality, purity, and potency characteristics, assuring safety and effectiveness. TGA is a typical method for assessing deterioration. The TGA is used to measure mass changes of one. Heating the sample across the temperature range at a specific rate and for a defined duration will result in mass loss due to solvent water loss and the formation of volatile degradation products.

4. TGA in soil examination

The primary goal of soil analysis is to measure the amount of soil organic carbon (SOC). It supplies the soil with both chemical and physical qualities, such as water storage capacity and nutrient cycling, which eventually influences seasonal crop yield. Fertile agricultural soil includes around 3-6% organic matter,

depending on soil type and land management. Many soil scientists and researchers are currently interested in studying SOC since different chemical, physical, ecological, and biological processes are dependent on SOC components, making it a better indicator of soil quality.

Soil is essential trace evidence in forensic science because it may attach to and transfer to other surfaces, particularly microscopic particles and organic substances. Soil can be gathered from the shoes of those present during the crime, clothing, any equipment used to assault the victims, burial materials, and the suspect's car, among other things. In recent years, some researchers have used thermal analytical methods, such as DSC and TGA, to identify soil organic matter in soil samples.

Unlocking thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) in the battle against "fake graphene" materials Commercial "graphene" products now on the market are "expensive graphite," not graphene, raising global worries among end users and the expanding multi-million dollar graphene sector. Since its discovery in 2004, graphene has been referred to as the material of the twenty-first century and a new disruptive technology, with significant research expenditure and expectations. These hopes were based on its exceptional characteristics and several potential uses in electronics, energy storage, composites, protective coatings, adsorbents, sensors, and medicine.

The GA technique is a sophisticated analytical instrument for the qualitative and quantitative examination of graphene materials, capable of providing accurate quality control, classifying generated FLG products on the market, and distinguishing between "fake graphene". This hypothesis is based on scientific data presented in the literature from TGA analysis of graphene materials, demonstrating that this approach has the capacity to discover non-graphene components based on unique changes in their thermal breakdown characteristics when compared to FLG. To test this idea, we first created verified control samples of FLG, reduced graphene oxide, and graphene oxide (GO), which confirmed the baseline TGA and first derivative (DTG) properties of their bulk powder forms.

Their main features, including the number of layers, particle size, structural flaws, crystallinity, proportion of non-graphitic carbon (sp³/sp²), elemental composition, and impurities, were confirmed.

5. Oxidation and combustion

The most basic material characterisation is the residue left after a reaction. For example, a combustion reaction might be examined by placing a sample into a thermogravimetric analyzer under normal circumstances. The thermogravimetric analyzer would initiate ion combustion in the sample by heating it above the ignition temperature. When the resultant TGA curve is displayed with the Y axis as a percentage of original mass, the residual at the curve's end point is visible. The most prevalent visible loss in TGA is oxidative mass loss. Combustion during TG analysis is shown by separate traces in the TGA thermograms generated.

When the weight and temperature are plotted against time, the first derivative plot shows a rapid slope shift that corresponds to the mass loss of the sample and the abrupt spike in temperature observed by the thermos pair. Beyond the oxidation of carbon produced by poorly managed weight loss, the mass loss might be caused by particles of smoke emitted during combustion caused by inconsistencies in the material itself. Weight losses on the same sample at several times can also be used to diagnose sample anisotropy. For example, sampling the top and bottom sides of a sample with scattered particles within can be used to identify sedimentation because thermograms do not overlap and indicate a gap between them if the particle distribution varies from side to side.

II. DIFFERENTIAL THERMAL ANALYSIS (DTA)

DTA is a thermal analysis technique that involves measuring the temperature difference between a sample and a reference compound during identical heat treatments. The reference material must be inert, and both the reference material and sample should undergo the same conditions and treatments^[10]. When the temperatures of the sample and the reference exhibit no difference, it indicates that the sample compound is thermally inert. This occurs because both the reference material and the sample are thermally inert, and the analysis is conducted relative to the reference material. DTA remains the most widely utilized thermal method of analysis. In DTA, the temperature of the sample is compared with that of an inert reference material while the temperature undergoes programmed changes. Initially, both temperatures remain identical until thermal events such as melting, decomposition, or changes in crystal structure occur. During an endothermic event within the sample, its temperature lags behind that of the reference, resulting in a minimum observed on the curve. Conversely, during an exothermic event, the temperature of the sample surpasses that of the

reference, indicating the enthalpy of the thermal event. For many issues, it is advantageous to employ both DTA and TGA since DTA events may be categorized as either involving mass change or not. TGA and DTA

may determine the melting point, glass transition temperature, crystalline, moisture content, thermal and oxidative stability, purity, transformation, and temperature.

Figure 2: Instrumentation of DTA

APPLICATION OF DTA

1. In preparation of glass ceramic made by iron tailing

Tailings are a type of solid industrial waste produced after separation. With the rapid expansion of the iron and steel sector, the proportion of iron ore tailings in industrial solid waste is rapidly increasing. Low-grade iron ore can create more tailings during the separation process, and a high volume of tailings will have a significant negative impact on the environment. Currently, iron tailings are mostly employed in areas where sophisticated technology is not required and value-added is minimal. If low ferrosilicon tailings can be utilized to create high-performance and low-cost glass-ceramic, it will be significant in terms of resource use and increasing the use of iron tailings; moreover, it will benefit the ecological environment. If the sample and reference materials are heated or cooled in the same conditions, DTA under temperature control by the software may assess the connection between temperature difference and temperature, providing useful information about material structural changes. DTA can help decide the glass-ceramic heat treatment system. Using differential thermal analysis technology and detecting various phases of the crystallization temperature, we can consciously regulate the crystallization temperature to generate the appropriate major phase and achieve the desired product performance. Glass-ceramic preparation may increase the usage of iron tailings to a greater degree,

opening up a new technique for complete use of low ferrosilicon iron tailings.

2. DTA in oils and fats

DTA cooling curves for certain synthetic glycerides, followed by curves for vegetable oils and fractions extracted from the oils using thin layer chromatography on silica gel-silver nitrate. Many of the curves may be intercepted using the known glyceride compositions of the oils.

3. Analytical Applications of DTA

Differential thermal analysis has been used for many years to detect phase transitions, particularly in minerals. In addition to its standard application in finding phase transformation temperatures, differential thermal analysis can be used as a control tool or as a routine tool for comparing comparable but not identical materials. As a control tool, it may be used to rapidly and readily separate raw materials. In such instances, the material's treatment must be updated if minor changes occur.

4. DTA in the study of isothermal and non-isothermal crystallization kinetics of coal fly ash based glasses

Knowledge of nucleation and crystallization kinetic factors, such as activation energy for crystal development and crystal growth process, is critical in the production of glass-ceramics with the appropriate

microstructure and characteristics. DTA is commonly used to study the crystallization kinetics of glasses. The differential thermal examination of glass samples is carried out using two methods: isothermal and non-isothermal. The Johnson meh-avrami equation (JMA) is commonly utilized for kinetic analysis of isothermal DTA data. The JMA method involves swiftly heating glass samples and holding them at a temperature above the glass transition point.

5. DTA in Cement Research

Differential thermal analysis (DTA) has lately gained prominence as a research method in cement chemistry. DTA is commonly used to identify various materials, but it may also be used to monitor processes by progressively heating the reactants to high temperatures. The use of sensitive equipment and correct calibration makes quantitative assessment of materials easier. Certain weakly crystalline compounds that are not easily recognized by x-ray diffraction have unique thermal peaks.

Although DTA is commonly used in clay mineralogy, it has only lately been expanded to other domains. The approach involves monitoring the heat changes caused by physical or chemical reactions happening during the slow heating of a sample. The DTA approach has been applied in a variety of sectors, including criminology, pyrotechnics, catalysis, coal chemistry, polymer systems, radiation, soap and lubrication systems, and will continue to be introduced to new areas of research.

The DTA method had its origin in 1887 when Le Chatelier applied thermal analysis to the study of the constitution of clays⁽¹⁻⁴⁾. Kalousek et al were probably first to introduce DTA in cement chemistry. The usefulness of the method was realized and discussed at the Third International Symposium on the Chemistry of Cements held in London in 1952, and since then several papers have appeared dealing with the DTA of

cementitious materials. Between 1952 and 1960, increasing attention was paid to the application of DTA in cement chemistry and at the Fourth International Symposium on the Chemistry of Cement, held in 1960; several investigators interpreted their results through thermogravimetric analysis.

6. Applications of DTA apparatus in high magnetic field

A differential thermal analysis (DTA) device has been designed for a commercial superconducting magnet. The DTA device could detect phase transition kinetics and thermodynamics in the presence and absence of a magnetic field. The preliminary results for eutectics are reported. The DTA curves show similarities at numerous rates regardless of the magnetic field; nevertheless, at the same rate, melting transformation appears to be unaffected by the magnetic field, but solidification may be slowed by inhibiting nucleation and crystal development in a magnetic field. It is expected that the DTA apparatus may be utilized to study the phase change of compounds of interest in a magnetic field.

III. DIFFERENTIAL SCANNING CALORIMETRY (DSC)

DSC is an analytical method that measures the amount of heat required to raise the temperature of a sample versus a reference as a function of temperature. Throughout the experiment, the temperature of both the sample and the reference is kept practically constant. DSC independently assesses the rate of heat movement between a sample and a standard at the same temperature. Data is collected by measuring differential heat flow as a function of temperature. DSC is useful for doing the same measurements as DTA and has the additional capacity of measuring heat capacities. The DSC's main benefit is its simplicity and quickness in detecting material changes. The glass transition is critical for understanding any polymeric material.

Figure 3: Instrumentation of DTA

APPLICATIONS OF DSC:

DSC has not been widely employed in the conservation profession, particularly in the research of painting layers. However, because no sample pre-treatment is necessary, DSC is a micro-destructive method (samples ranging from 0.5 to 1 mg may be evaluated), allowing it to provide quick and informative results. The purpose of this work is to describe relevant uses of DSC in the study of materials used in art. The investigations were carried out under oxygen flow in order to record the thermo-oxidative reactions of the organic binder or protection. In the first section of the article, materials of various chemical compositions were investigated to create a database of DSC profiles. Standard painting layers were examined after being intentionally deteriorated for 21 days with UV radiation (365 nm). When comparing the behavior of the treated and reference samples, it is possible to determine what types of changes the treatments have caused in the sample.

Another conceivable use for DSC is the investigation of film development; by studying raw, liquid binders, and various naturally aged films, a progression of the chemical structure may be observed. The sample is heated under oxygen to record its thermal response. Several interesting studies have been conducted that clearly indicated that differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) is a viable tool for assessing the oxidative degradation of organic matter (mediums, adhesives, and film components) in paintings. Many factors influence DSC tests, including the type of the inorganic pigment, the presence of a combination of binders and protective agents, and the sample's degradation narrative.

1. Glue:

Fish glue, deer glue, and donkey glue are all in the same family. Glue is made by heating skins, bones, and muscle tissues to around 80-90°C; this partially degrades the collagen, which is the major component, and gives it sticky characteristics. Collagen is a fibrous protein with linear polypeptide chains that are more or less parallel to one another. It also has a fairly rigid structure generated by often repeated glycine-proline-hydroxyproline sequences.

Collagen is made up of three protein strands linked together by strong hydrogen bonds. Glue is created when the inter chain hydrogen bonds break down due to water action. Glues may be derived from both animals and fish; however, fish glue appears to have poorer structural stability than animal glue. This might be attributed to a reduced percentage of

hydroxyproline and proline residues. When comparing the DSC profiles of the three glues, it is noticeable that deer and donkey glues display one huge peak.

2. Practical Food Applications of Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)

Food is frequently a complicated system with several compositions and structures. As a result, identifying foods might be difficult. Food has been studied using a variety of analytical procedures, including DSC. DSC is a thermal analysis technique that measures the temperature and heat fluxes associated with phase transitions in materials over time and at various temperatures. Such measurements can offer both quantitative and qualitative data on physical and chemical changes involving endothermic (energy-consuming) and exothermic (energy-producing) processes, as well as changes in heat capacity.

DSC is particularly useful for analyzing food systems since they are often heated or cooled during processing. The calorimetric data from DSC may be utilized directly to understand the thermal changes that the food system may go through during preparation or storage. DSC is simple to use, and in most circumstances, no extra sample preparation is necessary. The heat-cool-heat DSC software can determine the onset temperature, heat of fusion (ΔH), polymorphic behavior, and crystallization of oils and fats.

DSC for vegetable powders Food items are complex combinations of numerous chemicals, making it challenging to precisely calculate their glass transition (T_g) temperatures. Understanding the glass transition phenomena gives insights into the origins of the cohesiveness of many essential powders and influences the wettability or solubility of the powder, which is crucial for new product development.

Food typically contains water, either free or bound. The free water is connected to the water activity (A_w). The plasticization impact of water lowers the glass transition temperature, resulting in considerable changes in physicochemical and crystalline characteristics during storage. Moisture and temperature-induced loss of physical stability reduces flowability and increases caking tendency, while also affecting other physical qualities such as color to a lesser amount. A T_g is only detected for amorphous material.

Table 1: Types of samples used in DSC

TYPE OF SAMPLE	TYPE OF INFORMATION
Oils, fats and spreads	Onset temp of melt/crystallisation/polymorphic behaviour /oxidation stability
Flour and rice starch	Retrogradation /gelatinization/glass transition Tg
Vegetable powders	Glass transition Tg
Pastes and gels containing polysaccharides or gums.	Specific heat cp, onset temp of melt and crystallization.
Proteins	Denaturation /aggregation

DSC is used to compare batches of a product and investigate the melting behavior, which indicates changes in the crystalline structure of the fat or the content of the finished product. Different scanning rates are utilized to explore how chilling affects the crystallization of a given fat. The solid fat content (SFC) of a fat system can be calculated across a certain melting range. The solid fat content values are derived by the partial regions of DSC heating curves, typically between 5-60 °C, and compared to NMR data. To evaluate the aging of a lipid or end product, the sample is held at an isothermal temperature, which mimics refrigerator conditions. Comparing DSC thermograms of a fresh sample and after a given storage duration provides information on phase transitions during various storage circumstances.

3. DSC in the study of thermal energy storage

DSC is a flexible method for studying the behavior of materials that store energy through melting or solid-state transitions. Heating scans assess the enthalpy that can be stored, whereas cooling scans determine the enthalpy that can be retrieved from the material. Exotherms also give information about super cooling. The instrument system's automated and quick thermal cycling characteristics can be employed to expedite thermal degradation caused by the storage medium's daily duty cycle. These chemical interactions, as well as those between the medium and its confinement or with compounds introduced to increase performance, may be observed by changes in the temperature spectrum.

4. DSC in oils and fat research

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) is the most extensively utilized of the thermal methods accessible to analysts, and it gives a quick and simple way to collect a plethora of information about a material, regardless of its intended purpose. It has been used in a broad range of applications, including polymers and plastics, foods and medicines, glasses and ceramics, proteins, and life science materials; in fact, almost any

substance, allowing the analyst to swiftly quantify the item's fundamental characteristics. For boiling points and pressure DSC also calculates the sample's vapor pressure. Kinetic studies on the DSC can be carried out using scanning techniques, in which the sample is either heated through a temperature ramp or isothermally, in which the sample is kept at a constant temperature. The benefit of utilizing DSC for kinetic investigations is that it is often quicker and simpler than other approaches.

The usefulness of differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) for detecting water content in butter was assessed. There were strong correlation coefficients discovered between the water content and the enthalpies of ice melting/water crystallization. The correlation equations were used to compute the water content of seven different varieties of butter, and the results were compared to the values obtained using the reference technique. The discrepancy between the water content calculated by the reference technique and by DSC was between 0.2 and 2.6% for the observed enthalpy of ice melting, and between 1 and 5.6% for the enthalpy of water crystallization. Based on the results, it is possible to conclude that the ice melting enthalpy parameter can be utilized to detect adulterations or certify butter authenticity. The usefulness of differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) for detecting water content in butter was assessed. There were strong correlation coefficients discovered between the water content and the enthalpies of ice melting/water crystallization. The correlation equations were used to compute the water content of seven different varieties of butter, and the results were compared to the values obtained using the reference technique. The discrepancy in water content obtained by the reference technique and by DSC was between 0.2 and 2.6% for the observed enthalpy of ice melting and 1 to 5.6% for the enthalpy of water crystallization. Based on the findings, it is possible to conclude that the ice melting enthalpy parameter can be utilized to identify adulterations or certify butter authenticity.

DIFFERENTIATION BETWEEN TGA, DTA & DSC

Table 2: Differences between TGA, DTA, DSC

TGA is Thermal Gravimetric Analysis	DTA is Differential Thermal Analysis.	DSC is Differential Scanning Calorimetry
The change of the mass of a sample with the change of temperature is observed and analysed	The Temperature difference developed between a sample and a reference compound is measured at identical heat treatments.	The heat flow is measured against the temperature change at a particular time.
Used to analyze inorganic materials, metals, polymers, plastics, ceramics, glasses and composite materials.	Used to analyze thermal properties of minerals for the characterization of polymers and biological materials.	Used to analyze proteins, antibodies, etc.
Sample can be used as a solid substance	Sample can be used as a solid substance	Sample is always Liquid
TGA measures the mass changes due to thermal events	DTA measures the temperature differences indicating thermal events	DSC measures the heat flow associated with the thermal events.
A thermogram is drawn between mass gain or loss Vs temperature or time	A thermogram is drawn between temperature difference Vs temperature or time	A thermogram is drawn between heat flow Vs temperature or time.
Used for analyzing thermal stability, compositional analysis and in studying decomposition	Used for detection of phase transitions and reaction temperatures	Used in qualitative analysis of heat flow, specific heat and enthalpy of transitions.

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